

KOSHI-BUNYAKOVSKIY INTEGRAL TENGSIZLIGI VA UNING QO‘LLANISHI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Bu maqolada matematik analizdagi murakkab integral tengsizliklarni osonlik bilan yechishga qodir bo‘lgan Koshi-Bunyakovskiy tengsizligi hamda uni qo‘llanishiga doir bir qancha misollar berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: funksiya, uzluksiz, integral, tengsizlik.

ABSTRACT

This article presents the Cauchy-Buniakovsky inequality, which can easily solve complex integral inequalities in mathematical analysis, and several examples of its application.

Key words: function, continuous, integral, inequality.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлено неравенство Коши-Буняковского, с помощью которого легко решаются сложные интегральные неравенства в математическом анализе, и несколько примеров его применения.

Ключевые слова: функция, непрерывный, интеграл, неравенство.

Koshi Bunyakovskiy tengsizligi: Aytaylik bizga $[a, b]$ da integrallanuvchi ikkita $f(x)$ va $g(x)$ funksiyalar berilgan, u holda quyidagi o‘rinli:

$$\left(\int_a^b f(x)g(x)dx \right)^2 \leq \int_a^b f^2(x)dx \int_a^b g^2(x)dx \quad (1)$$

Endi ushbu tengsizlikni bir qancha misollarda qo‘llab ko‘raylik:

1-misol.

$f : [0,1] \rightarrow R$ uzluksiz funksiya berilgan bo'lsin. U holda quyidagi tengsizlikni isbotlang:

$$\left(\int_0^1 f(x)dx\right)^2 \leq \int_0^1 f^2(x)dx$$

Isbot: $g(x) = 1$ funksiya deb $f(x)$ funksiyaga nisbatan (1) tengsizlikni qo'llaymiz:

$$\left(\int_0^1 f(x) \cdot 1 dx\right)^2 \leq \left(\int_0^1 f^2(x)dx\right) \left(\int_0^1 1^2 dx\right) = \int_0^1 f^2(x)dx \text{ isbotlandi.}$$

2-misol.

$f : [0,1] \rightarrow R$ uzluksiz funksiya quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsin:

$$\int_0^1 f(x)dx = 1 \quad \text{va} \quad \int_0^1 xf(x)dx = 1$$

U holda isbotlang:

$$\int_0^1 f^2(x)dx \geq 4$$

Isbot: $g(x) = 3x - 1$ funksiya olib $f(x)$ uchun (1) tengsizlikni qo'llaymiz:

$$\left(\int_0^1 f(x)(3x-1)dx\right)^2 \leq \int_0^1 f^2(x)dx \cdot \int_0^1 (3x-1)^2 dx$$

$$\int_0^1 f(x)(3x-1)dx = \int_0^1 3xf(x)dx - \int_0^1 f(x)dx = 3 - 1 = 2$$

$$\int_0^1 (3x-1)^2 dx = \int_0^1 (9x^2 - 6x + 1)dx = (3x^3 - 3x^2 + x) \Big|_0^1 = 1$$

$$\text{Demak, } 2^2 \leq \int_0^1 f^2(x)dx \cdot 1 \quad 4 \leq \int_0^1 f^2(x)dx \text{ Isbotlandi.}$$

3-misol.

$f : [0,1] \rightarrow R$ differensiallanuvchi funksiya quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradi:

$$\int_0^1 f(x)dx = 1 \quad \text{va} \quad \int_0^1 xf(x)dx = 1 \quad \text{u holda isbotlang:}$$

$$\int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx \geq 30$$

Isbot. $g(x) = x^2 - x$ funksiya olib, $f'(x)$ uchun (1) tengsizlikni qo'llaymiz:

$$\left(\int_0^1 (x^2 - x) f'(x) dx\right)^2 \leq \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx \cdot \int_0^1 (x^2 - x)^2 dx$$

$$\int_0^1 (x^2 - x) f'(x) dx = [(x^2 - x) f(x)] \Big|_0^1 - \int_0^1 (2x - 1) f(x) dx = -2 \int_0^1 x f(x) dx + \int_0^1 f(x) dx = -2 + 1 = -1$$

$$\int_0^1 (x^2 - x)^2 dx = \int_0^1 (x^4 - 2x^3 + x^2) dx = \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{1}{30}$$

Demak $(-1)^2 \leq \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx \cdot \frac{1}{30} \Rightarrow 30 \leq \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx$ isbotlandi.

4-misol.

$f : [0,1] \rightarrow R$ uzluksiz differensiallanuvchi funksiya uchun $f(0) = f(1) = 0$ bo'lsin, u holda isbotlang:

$$\int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx \geq 12 \left(\int_0^1 f(x) dx\right)^2$$

Isbot. $g(x) = x - \frac{1}{2}$ funksiya olib $f'(x)$ uchun (1) tengsizlikni qo'llaymiz:

$$\left(\int_0^1 \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) f'(x) dx\right)^2 \leq \left(\int_0^1 \left(x^2 - x + \frac{1}{4}\right) dx\right) \cdot \left(\int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx\right) = \frac{1}{12} \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx$$

$$\left(\int_0^1 \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) f'(x) dx\right)^2 = \left[\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) f(x)\right] \Big|_0^1 - \int_0^1 f(x) dx = -\int_0^1 f(x) dx$$

Demak, $\left(\int_0^1 f(x) dx\right)^2 \leq \frac{1}{12} \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx \Rightarrow 12 \left(\int_0^1 f(x) dx\right)^2 \leq \int_0^1 (f'(x))^2 dx$.

5-misol.

$f : [0,1] \rightarrow R$ ikki marta differensiallanuvchi funksiya uchun $\int_0^1 f(x) dx = \frac{f(x)}{2}$

o‘rinli bo‘lsin. U holda quyidagi isbotlang:

$$\int_0^1 (f''(x))^2 dx \geq 30 \cdot f^2(0)$$

Isbot: $g(x) = x^2 - x$ funksiya olib $f''(x)$ uchun (1) tengsizlikni qo‘llaymiz,

$$\left[\int_0^1 (x^2 - x) f''(x) dx \right]^2 \leq \int_0^1 (x^2 - x)^2 dx \cdot \int_0^1 (f''(x))^2 dx = \frac{1}{30} \int_0^1 (f''(x))^2 dx$$

$$\int_0^1 (x^2 - x) f''(x) dx = \left[(x^2 - x) f'(x) \right]_0^1 - \int_0^1 f'(x)(2x - 1) dx = \left[-(2x - 1) f(x) \right]_0^1 +$$

$$+ \int_0^1 2f(x) dx = -f(1) + f(0) \cdot 2 \cdot \frac{f(1)}{2} = f(0)$$

$$\text{Demak, } f^2(0) \leq \frac{1}{30} \int_0^1 (f''(x))^2 dx \quad 30f(0) \leq \int_0^1 (f''(x))^2 dx .$$

Shuni ta‘kidlab o‘tishimiz kerakki, yuqoridagi misollarga o‘xshash misollar so‘nggi yillarda talabalar o‘rtasida xalqaro matematika musobaqalarida muntazam uchrab turibdi. Endi har bir o‘quvchi ushbu tengsizlikni qo‘llashga harakat qilib ko‘rsa, uning ahamiyati qanchalik katta ekanligini yanada yaxshi anglab yetadi.

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